

In situ electrochemical characterisation of Cu_xO-based gas-diffusion electrodes (GDEs) for CO₂ electrocatalytic reduction in the presence and absence of liquid electrolyte and relationship with C₂⁺ products formation

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Abstract

Copper oxide-based gas-diffusion electrodes (Cu_xO/GDEs) for CO₂ electrocatalytic reduction are investigated in presence and absence of liquid electrolyte (liquid- and gas-phase operations) in terms of (i) catalytic reactivity in compact-design flow cells (with the electrodes located on the two sides of a Nafion membrane) and (ii) in situ electrochemical characterisation by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), cyclic voltammetry (CV) and chronoamperometry (CA). On the same electrocatalyst, the adoption of liquid- or gas-phase operations induces significant changes in the catalytic behaviour with formation of C₂⁺ chemicals observed only in gas-phase.

Parallel tests by EIS, complemented by CV and CA measurements, evidence that the catalytic properties of these electrodes, and in turn the selectivity paths, are largely determined by transport limitations rather than only by the intrinsic properties of the electrocatalysts. The EIS technique, used here for the first time to compare liquid- and gas-phase operations, has proved to be a strategic tool, providing insights into the critical factors needed to optimise performance beyond the properties of the electrocatalysts themselves.

1. Introduction

The process of electrocatalytic reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in mild conditions is a great opportunity to convert H₂O and CO₂ into valuable products by using renewable electrical energy [1]. Most of the studies are usually made in conventional electrochemical cells with the electrodes immersed in a liquid electrolyte solution. Cathodic and anodic zones are used for CO₂ reduction and water oxidation, respectively, and are separated by a proton (or anion) exchange membrane. The solubility of CO₂ in the electrolyte often limits the surface coverage of the electrode, and for this reason the predominant products observed are C₁ chemicals, such as CO [2] and HCOOH [3]. Nevertheless, the formation of C₂⁺ (products with two or more carbon atoms) is also detected depending on the catalyst and operating conditions (applied voltage, current density, pH) [4]. While many studies have investigated the electrocatalytic behaviour of metals/metal oxides in CO₂ reduction and their optimization for the selective formation towards HCOOH [5–8] or CO [9–11], from an industrial perspective the production of C₂⁺ results more interesting, because they have a greater added value and do not require further down streaming processing [12] (although many options were reported for this aspect [13]).

The formation of C₂⁺ can be enhanced, in general, by a higher surface coverage of the electrode by CO₂ and/or adspecies generated by its reduction. We earlier demonstrated that this higher in situ surface coverage during CO₂ electro-reduction can be induced by so-called gas-phase operations (indicated also as

electrolyte-less conditions or zero gap) [14–17]. In this approach, the membrane is used not only as the element of separation between cathodic and anodic zones, but also as a solid electrolyte to close the ionic circuit between the two electrodes, feeding CO₂ through a gas-diffusion electrode (GDE) [18,19]. This cell design provides various advantages, among which (i) a more compact design, easier to be scaled-up and to develop stacked electrocatalytic reactors, (ii) elimination of gas diffusion problems through the liquid bulk, (iii) no CO₂ solubility limitations or influence on the mass transfer, and (iv) easier recovery of liquid products.

Now, there is a rising interest on this type of electrocatalytic reactors for CO₂ reduction based on GDEs [20]. While it was clearly evidenced that the same electrocatalysts give rise to different products and selectivity depending on whether or not they are in contact with the bulk electrolyte [15,18], the exact understanding of this difference in terms of working state during electrocatalytic operations is far from being clearly determined. Most of the mechanistic studies regarding C₂⁺ formation are based on methodologies not accounting for the effect of the electrolyte, the diffusion of CO₂ to the electrocatalyst, the concentration of adspecies on the electrode surface, and how these aspects are influenced by the application of an electrical potential [21–26]. While attention in the literature has especially focused on electrocatalyst design, we showed earlier that, for example, a non-selective electrocatalyst towards C₂⁺ (i.e., Pt) can be turned into selective (up to 60% faradaic selectivity) when a sufficient surface concentration of CO₂ is provided by modifying the GDE with CO₂-adsorbing elements [14]. Thus, under proper conditions of surface concentration of CO₂ and/or adspecies derived from CO₂ reduction, even an electrocatalyst unable to form C₂⁺ (based on current mechanistic indications) may instead become selective to form C₂⁺. This result clearly highlights the role of a better understanding and characterization of the working state of electrocatalysts during CO₂ electro-reduction, and how different reactor operation and electrode design can in turn influence this aspect, as in general occurs for other electrocatalytic processes [27,28].

For sake of conciseness, we hereinafter indicate as *liquid-phase* the operations in the presence of a bulk liquid electrolyte (as in conventional operations) and *gas-phase* the operations when this bulk electrolyte is absent. In the latter case, the membrane itself acts as a solid electrolyte, with the electrocatalyst deposited on one side of a gas-diffusion layer (GDL) substrate in direct contact with the membrane to form the GDE (zero gap), acting also as an electron collector/distributor.

Recently, although still to a limited extent, activities about characterization in operando of electrocatalysts for CO₂ reduction have been growing [29–36]. However, these studies mainly focused on understanding factors related to the electrocatalyst itself, rather than on the aspects mentioned before. No studies on the different reactivity between liquid- and gas-phase operations on the same electrocatalyst, as a way to distinguish between the intrinsic electrocatalyst properties and those deriving from external factors determining the surface coverage (such as transport limitation, CO₂ solubility, effect of the potential, etc.) have been addressed so far. A strategic tool capable of providing new insights into these aspects and explaining the real reasons of the large difference in electrocatalytic behaviour between liquid- and gas-phase operations is highly desirable.

In this direction, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a useful tool to investigate the electro-reduction of CO₂ [37]. The EIS technique is a widely used in situ/operando characterization method [38–40], also used for CO₂ reduction but typically adopted to study aspects different from the dynamics of surface species over electrocatalysts, except for a few cases but not comparing liquid- and gas-phase operations [41].

The aim of this work is thus to demonstrate how charge transfer phenomena can influence the electrocatalytic activity and address the process selectivity in CO₂ electro-reduction. A careful in situ electrochemical characterization by EIS shows, in fact, that the reactor conditions (liquid- or gas-phase operations) lead to different individual charge transfer resistances within the cell, unveiling why the same electrocatalytic material can behave quite differently if the cathode is processed in gas phase (in absence of a liquid electrolyte, thus favouring the formation of >C₁ chemicals) or under conventional liquid conditions. There are some recent studies focusing on the effects of mass transport phenomena rather than on the intrinsic properties of the electrocatalysts [42–45]. However, as far as we know, no similar works comparing zero-gap reactor conditions with conventional liquid phase operation (using EIS as the strategic tool) have

been published so far.

For the scope, copper-based (Cu_xO) gas diffusion electrodes were prepared and assembled in our compact-design electrochemical devices, and then characterized by EIS. Experimental EIS analyses were carried out under a continuous stream of pure CO_2 , but also blank experiments with N_2 inert gas (no CO_2) were performed to find out a correlation between the individual charge transfer resistances and proton reduction (excluding CO_2 reduction). Finally, the electrodes were tested for CO_2 electro-reduction both in liquid and gas phase, and products were quantified for a direct comparison. While the conventional liquid approach led mainly to CO and formic acid (evidencing that no specific activity of these Cu-based electrocatalysts towards $>\text{C1}$ formation exists), tests in gas phase allowed to obtain different products such as ethanol, acetaldehyde, and traces of acetic acid, propionaldehyde and butanone, in addition to CO and H_2 .

Note, however, that this study aims at understanding (for the first time through EIS) the differences in reactivity between liquid- and gas- phase operations (on the same electrocatalyst), not at maximizing the performance of the electrocatalyst itself. For example, a recent study by Xu et al. [46] reported high Faradaic Efficiency (FE) of 91 % at - 0.7 V vs. RHE for electrocatalytic CO_2 -to-ethanol conversion. However, this high performance was due to the specific technique developed for the preparation of the catalysts (i.e., an amalgamated Cu–Li method). The presence of other elements such as Li, and of an amalgam with possible phase separation under potential application may interfere in EIS analysis. Similarly, Ma et al. [47] reported a fluorine-modified copper catalyst, showing a $\text{C2}+$ (mainly ethylene and ethanol) FE of 80 % at a very high current density (1.6 A cm^{-2}) in CO_2 electrocatalytic reduction using a flow cell. The presence of F may also interfere in EIS analysis. In general, copper oxides were proposed as promising electrocatalysts to prepare efficient GDEs for CO_2 reduction [48–51], but to enhance electrocatalytic activity and improve selectivity towards specific products (such as methanol or other superior alcohols), copper was used in combination with other metals or metal oxides, such as Cu-Zn [52–54], Cu-Bi [55], and other bimetallic [56] or metal-organic framework-based catalysts [57,58]. However, the novelty of this work is to unveil the real reasons why charge transfer limitations change when a liquid electrolyte is not used (i.e., gas-phase conditions). For that, we have avoided the addition of other elements than copper to the electrocatalyst to eliminate any kind of interference.

Note also that a recent review remarked that a combined use of GDE and micro flow-cell improves the electrocatalytic performances in CO_2 reduction [59]. The approach used in our work (indicated as gas-phase operation) is analogous to that remarked in this review as the preferential approach. Therefore, this work can provide: (i) additional indications to understand the motivations of the enhanced performance with this electrochemical reactor configuration, (ii) insights into the properties of electrocatalysts, electrodes and reactor and their optimized integration to maximize performance in CO_2 electro-reduction. It is perhaps a unique and valuable methodology able to address all these aspects at the same time.

2. Material and methods

Chemicals

All reagents were purchased commercially and used without any purification. Potassium hydrogen carbonate (KHCO_3), 2-propanol ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}$) and Milli-Q water were purchased from Carlo Erba, while Copper(II) chloride dihydrate ($\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), L-Ascorbic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$) and NaOH (pellets) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Cu_2O wet precipitation synthesis

Cu_2O powder was prepared by a facile wet precipitation synthesis:

0.85 g of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in 500 mL of distilled water under stirring at 60°C , following by the addition of 50 mL of 2 M NaOH. After stirring the solution for 30 min, 50 mL of a 0.6 M ascorbic acid solution were added. The formation of a red copper oxide precipitate was observed and, after about 3 h of stirring at 60°C , a complete precipitation was reached. The obtained precipitate was cooled at room temperature, washed many times with ethanol and water, collected by centrifugation and dried in a vacuum

oven at 60 °C overnight.

Calcination to CuO

CuO powder was obtained by calcinating the as-prepared Cu₂O in a muffle at 450 °C for 1 h at 10 °C min⁻¹.

Electrode preparation

Cu_xO powders were deposited on carbon-based substrates to prepare the electrodes. In detail, a weighted amount of fresh copper oxide catalyst (depending on the desired final loading) was mixed with 8 mL of isopropanol and 50 µL of 10 % Nafion® perfluorated and sonicated until formation of a stable suspension (15 min). The resulting ink was deposited by spray coating onto a pre-heated porous carbon based gas-diffusion layer (GDL, Sigracet® 29BCE, supplied by Ion Power), acting as the support, to allow the evaporation of the solvent and fix uniformly the powder on the electrode surface.

The initial amount of copper oxide was chosen in order to obtain three different final loadings on the GDL (1, 5 and 10 mg cm⁻²).

XRD characterization

A D2 Phaser Bruker diffractometer equipped with a Ni β-filtered Cu- Kα radiation source, operating at 30 kV and 10 mA, was used to perform X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis on Cu_xO-GDL electrodes, in order to investigate their phase composition and crystalline size. In detail, data were collected in a 2θ range from 10° to 80° at a scanning rate of 0.025°s⁻¹ in PSD (position-sensitive-detector) fast scan mode adopting the following parameters: step size of 0.040° and time per step of 165 s. The detector was a Lynxeye (1D mode) with a PSD opening of 5.008°, lower discriminator of 0.110 V and lipper discriminator of 0.250 V. Other settings are: Ka2 ratio 0.5 and kβ 1.39222 Å. JCPDS database of reference compounds was used to identify the diffraction peaks.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

Analysis by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) of Cu_xO/ GDEs was performed in two electrochemical systems working in liquid- and gas-phase, under the same conditions as for the electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction tests, which will be described in the next section.

In both cases, Cyclic voltammetry (CV) analysis was carried out before the EIS measurements to stabilize the reaction system and reach a steady-state equilibrium. The EIS measurements were performed in a frequency range from 1 × 10⁵ to 0.1 Hz and amplitude of 0.01 V_{rms}.

Copper-based electrodes were also analysed in a reference system (useful for comparison with the literature), i.e., the redox couple ferrocyanide/ferricyanide and Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) as the supporting electrolyte. Specifically, the EIS analysis was performed in 1 M PBS and 5 mM potassium ferrocyanide solution at applied potential of 0.3 V. The working electrode was a modified screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) including: (i) a working carbon planar electrode (4 mm in diameter); (ii) a silver pseudo-reference electrode and (iii) a carbon counter electrode. The SPCE electrode was then modified by depositing Cu_xO powder on the working planar electrode. Further details are reported in Supporting Information (SI).

CO₂ electroreduction setups

The electrocatalytic tests were carried out both in liquid- and gas-phase. The **liquid-phase operations** were initially used to both characterize the electrodes from the electrochemical point of view and analyse the electrocatalytic activity in presence of a liquid electrolyte. These tests were carried out in a compact homemade electrochemical device, made of Plexiglas and working in a three-electrode configuration (see pictures in Fig. S1 and scheme in Fig. S2a in the SI) [60–62]. More in detail, the copper-based electrode (working electrode, 1 × 1 cm) was immersed in 0.1 M KHCO₃ aqueous electrolyte, while a platinum ring

was used as the counter-electrode, located at the anode compartment separated from the cathode by a proton exchange membrane (Nafion® 115, supplied by Ion Power) and working in 0.1 or 3.6 M KHCO₃ aqueous electrolyte. The higher KHCO₃ concentration at the anode (3.6 M, corresponding to its solubility in water)

was used only for the electrocatalytic tests at higher voltage (-0.8 V vs. RHE) when a higher availability of OH⁻ was necessary for water oxidation. An Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) electrode (supplied by AMEL) was used as the reference electrode and located very close to the working electrode to minimize over-potential (series resistance). The potential values were then translated into RHE (Reversible Hydrogen Electrode) voltages by using the following equation:

$$E_{(\text{RHE})} = E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.059 \text{ pH} + 0.21 \quad (1)$$

A continuous recirculation of catholyte/anolyte between each half-cell (cathode and anode) and two independent reservoir containers was guaranteed by means of a peristaltic pump working at a liquid flow rate of 50 mL min⁻¹. 20 mL·min⁻¹ of pure CO₂ was flowed into the catholyte reservoir in connection with the cathode compartment of the cell, in order to saturate the KHCO₃ solution. At the equilibrium, a pH of 6.78 was reached in the catholyte before starting the electrochemical tests.

The presence of gas products from the cathode outlet stream (H₂, CH₄, CO, C₂H₄, C₂H₆) was checked by a Gas Chromatograph (MicroGC GCX Pollution Analytic Equipment), having a sensitivity of 1–2 ppm, by sampling from the cathodic reservoir every 10 min. The liquid catholyte was instead analysed by Ion Chromatography (IC Metrohm 940 Professional, column Metrohm Organic Acids) to detect the presence of liquid products such as formic acid, acetic acid and oxalic acid (sensitivity of 0.5–1.0 ppm). The presence of other liquid products (i.e., methanol, ethanol, methyl formate, isopropanol, acetone and others) was checked by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS Thermo 1310-Tsq 8000 Evo, column Stabilwax), having a sensitivity of 1–5 ppm depending on the compounds. Each electrocatalytic test in liquid-phase was performed by following an accurate electrochemical protocol including equilibration, preliminary cyclic voltammetry, evaluation of capacitance, chronoamperometry test, post-evaluation of capacitance and cyclic voltammetry.

As reported elsewhere [31], preliminary tests, including tests with labelled CO₂, showed that the products detected derived from CO₂ electro-reduction. The cited reference also reports the better reliability of the methodology used here to analyse the products of CO₂ electro-reduction in comparison with alternative methods such as NMR. The **gas-phase operations** were performed in a similar compact homemade electrochemical device, but working with no liquid electrolyte in the cathode, also indicated as electrolyte-less or zero gap conditions [63]. A schematic depiction of the gas-phase device is shown in Fig. S2b in the SI. In detail, the cell is made of two compartments: (i) a gas cathodic chamber (with gas inlet and outlet) where CO₂ is fed and goes in contact with the back side of the GDL; (ii) a liquid anodic chamber, where the electrolyte (anolyte: aqueous solution at different KHCO₃ concentrations) is recirculated between the anode and a liquid reservoir. A proton exchange membrane (Nafion® 115, supplied by Ion Power) is assembled by hot-pressing with the GDL physically separating the two chambers and allowing the transport of H⁺ from the anolyte to the electrocatalytic material for the reduction reactions. In this configuration, the electrocatalytic material (Cu_xO) is located in the middle between the GDL and the Nafion® membrane. A platinum counter electrode (Pt rod) and a reference electrode (Ag/AgCl, 3 M KCl) are placed inside the liquid anodic compartment, very close to the GDL/membrane assembly to minimize overpotential. The gaseous stream coming out from the gas chamber goes to a cold ice trap (0.001 M H₂SO₄ aqueous solution) to collect the less volatile organic compounds, and finally to the Gas Chromatograph for the detection of gaseous products (see above). The absorbed liquid in the cold trap and the liquid anolyte are finally analysed by IC and GC/MS for the detection of organic compounds, such as formic acid, acetic acid, methanol, ethanol, methyl formate, etc. The working electrode has an active area of about 2 cm².

3. Results

Investigation of charge transfer phenomena by EIS

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is a useful technique to evaluate charge transfer phenomena occurring in electrochemical devices [64], and it was recently indicated as a powerful tool to investigate the electro-reduction of CO₂ [37].

Fig. 1a shows the Nyquist plots obtained for CuO/GDL electrode analysed in a conventional liquid-phase

electrochemical system at different applied potentials, with the cathode immersed in a liquid electrolyte saturated with CO₂ (as described in the experimental part). The experimental data are represented by points, while the dashed lines refer to the fitting curves processed through software simulation of appropriate equivalent circuits. Specifically, for applied potentials ranging from - 0.4 to - 0.8 V vs. RHE, two-time constants were obtained by fitting (see Fig. 1b), while a simpler electrical circuit (one-constant) was used to model the analysis at - 1.0 V vs. RHE (see Fig. 1c). The latter is a basic circuit that includes the resistor R_s in series with the parallel circuit consisting of the resistor R_{ct} and the equivalent element CPE (constant phase element). The intercept in x-axis refers to the series resistance (R_s), whereas the diameter of trivial arc (semicircle) is the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}). The R_s resistance is mainly related to the electrical wires used to connect the cell to the measuring system, and also includes the resistance gap between working and reference electrodes. The charge transfer resistance R_{ct}, instead, refers to the whole electrochemical process (i.e., both the reactions occurring on the electrode surfaces) and it is strongly related to the cell voltage. Note also that, instead of a simple capacitor, we used the element CPE, which models the behaviour of a double-layer, which is an imperfect capacitor [65].

In the two-constant fitting (used for most of the potentials, except for -1.0 V), two different charge transfer resistances were considered (R_{ct}' and R_{ct}). The Body plot reported in Fig. S4 (in SI) evidences better the presence of two constants. While the first semicircle R_{ct}' (at high frequency) is only slightly dependent on the potential, the low frequency process strongly varies with the applied voltage. We can attribute the high frequency R_{ct}' to the charge transport (ionic migration) in liquid phase towards the reaction site, while the low frequency R_{ct} reflects the charge transfer due to the reduction process. A similar behaviour was observed by Wang et al. [66] analysing a two-layer rolled Sn-loaded gas diffusion electrode processed in a microbial electrolysis cell for the electrochemical reduction of CO₂. In our analysis, the applied voltage of - 1.0 V vs. RHE is high enough to speed up ionic migration, with no semicircle observed at high frequency.

The EIS analysis was also made in the same electrochemical device replacing CO₂ with a N₂ inert gas stream (see the Nyquist plots obtained at different applied potentials in Fig. S5 in SI). Fitting of data was done with the same equivalent circuits adopted for CO₂ analysis. Comparing these data with those in Fig. 1a results evident that the profiles of the low frequency R_{ct} against the applied potential do not show relevant differences of charge transfer resistance (due to the electrochemical process) between CO₂ and N₂ environments. The analysis under N₂ stream excludes the reaction of CO₂ reduction (although this test was performed in KHCO₃ liquid electrolyte and small amount of CO₂ could be present). This is a clear indication that proton reduction is dominant in liquid-phase, and that protons compete with CO₂ intermediate species in the adsorption onto the electrocatalytic active sites, favouring their early desorption to produce CO and formic acid (which need only two electrons).

Fig. 2 shows, instead, the Nyquist plots obtained by analysing the same CuO/GDL electrode at different applied potentials in the gas-phase electrochemical system. We remark that no liquid electrolyte is present in the cathode compartment, being the GDL directly fed with a gaseous stream of CO₂ (as described in the experimental part). For all the potentials applied, EIS analysis reveals a process based on only one constant, with a simple equivalent electrical circuit fitting well the experimental data. Thus, the absence of a liquid electrolyte at the cathode side allows solving charge transport issues, with no measurements of resistances associated to ionic migration as instead clearly observed at high frequency by EIS analysis performed in conventional liquid-phase electrochemical devices.

Fig. 1. a) Nyquist plots for CuO/GDL electrode at different applied potential obtained in a conventional liquid-phase electrochemical device saturated with CO₂. b) two-constant circuit model used to fit analyses at -0.4, -0.6 and -0.8 V vs. RHE. c) simple one-constant circuit model used to fit analysis at -1.0 V vs. RHE.

Fig. 2. Nyquist plots for CuO/GDL electrode at different applied potential obtained in an unconventional gas-phase electrochemical device fed with CO₂. A simple one-constant circuit model was used to fit all the analyses.

The series resistances (R_s), which is given by the x-axis intercept in Nyquist plot, is about 52 Ω for gas-phase tests, much higher than the R_s values measured in liquid phase (i.e., about 2 Ω). However, this is only due to the position of the reference electrode, which in gas phase is necessarily located in the anode part (being no liquid electrolyte in the cathode). Although the reference electrode is located as much as close to the working electrode, the measurement of R_s includes the resistance of Nafion membrane (which is between the two electrodes).

The comparison between the charge transfer resistances (R_{ct}) in gas and liquid phase provides useful indications. Table 1 reports the values of R_{ct} calculated by fitting the EIS data for the two systems (for the liquid phase, the R_{ct} values of the semicircle at low frequency are considered).

The charge transfer resistance due to the electrochemical process is in general lower for gas-phase analysis, especially at lower potentials (at -1.0 V vs. RHE, the two R_{ct} values converge to about 6 Ω). This indicates that a gas-phase approach is more convenient in terms of energy losses, as the individual resistances are minimized if no electrolyte is used in the cathode compartment.

With the aim to distinguish between CO_2 and proton reduction, we also made blank tests in gas phase by replacing CO_2 with inert gas (i.e., N_2). Fig. S6 shows the Nyquist plots at different applied potentials. Also feeding N_2 , the EIS analysis can be fitted using a simple equivalent circuit model based on one constant. However, the R_{ct} values obtained in N_2 are much higher than the values observed in CO_2 , as showed in Fig. 2. If only N_2 is fed into the GDL, no CO_2 reduction can occur and protons (coming from the anode part through the Nafion membrane) diffuse slowly, resulting in a high charge transfer resistance. In presence of CO_2 gas stream, instead, the gas transport of CO_2 through the GDL is very fast, and the local concentration of CO_2 on the electrode surface is higher with respect to CO_2 supplying in liquid-phase configuration (which is limited by the low solubility of CO_2 in aqueous solutions).

Fig. 3 summarizes the results in terms of charge transfer resistance (Ω) as a function of the potential applied (V) for tests feeding CO_2 or N_2 for liquid-phase operations (a) and gas-phase operations (b).

Table 1

Charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) for CuO/GDL electrode at different applied potential obtained by fitting EIS data: comparison between liquid- and gas-phase operations. For liquid phase, the R_{ct} values refer to low-frequency semicircle.

<i>Applied voltage (V vs. RHE)</i>	<i>R_{ct} in liquid phase (Ω)</i>	<i>R_{ct} in gas phase (Ω)</i>
-0.4	213	93.9
-0.6	32.8	18.0
-0.8	15.9	9.0
-1.0	5.8	6.0

Fig. 3. a) Charge transfer resistance related to the reduction process (R_{ct} at low frequency obtained by Nyquist plots) versus the applied potential for CuO/GDL electrode analysed in a conventional liquid-phase electrochemical device saturated with CO_2 or N_2 . b) Charge transfer resistance (R_{ct} obtained by Nyquist plots) versus the applied potential for CuO/GDL electrode analysed in an un-conventional gas-phase electrochemical device fed with CO_2 or N_2 .

To demonstrate the electrocatalytic activity of CuO, blank EIS ana- lytic tests were also performed using bare GDL (no CuO deposited). Fig. S7 in SI shows the Nyquist plots obtained by analysing the bare GDL electrode at different applied potentials in the gas-phase configuration. The measured R_{ct} values are about two orders of magnitude higher for bare GDL with respect to CuO/GDL, evidencing a good performance of CuO as electrocatalyst for CO_2 reduction.

EIS measurements were also carried out by depositing CuO on a commercial screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) analysed in 5 mL of electrolyte using 5 mM potassium ferrocyanide and 1 M PBS solution as the supporting electrolyte. The Nyquist and Bode plots were fitted with two-time constants, similarly to EIS analysis in liquid phase, providing charge transfer resistance values (R_{ct}' and R_{ct}) of 4.0 and 28.2 k Ω , respectively (see Fig. S8 in SI).

XRD and SEM analysis

The phase composition of the Cu_xO electrocatalysts was investigated by XRD and the obtained diffraction patterns are shown in Fig. S9 (in SI) in the region between 10° and 80° . For the fresh powder Cu_2O synthesized by wet precipitation process (yellow line in Fig. S9a), the presence of impurities can be excluded and the reflection planes present at 29.7° , 36.6° , 42.5° , 61.6° , 73.7° , and 77.5° refer to the planes (110), (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222) belonging to the cuprous oxide, respectively (JCPDS 05–0667). The Cu_xO /GDEs were analysed after the whole electrochemical testing series in liquid phase (concluding at -0.8 V vs RHE). Due to the reductive environment at the cathode side, these samples show the presence of metallic copper (Cu^0), however not detected for the lowest catalyst loading (1 mg cm^{-2}). Moreover, additional peaks were detected, especially for the used Cu_2O /GDL sample with 5 mg cm^{-2} loading, probably due to Cu_2O corrosion in presence of KHCO_3 , forming copper carbonate-like species. A comparison between XRD patterns of Cu_2O and CuO was also reported in Fig. S9b.

The morphology of the synthesized catalysts, investigated by SEM, is shown in Fig. S10 (in SI). Both Cu_2O and CuO materials are characterized by a similar pattern with presence of packed nanocubes, with a size ranging from 100 to 200 nm.

Protocol for electrochemical reduction tests in liquid phase

The electrocatalysts were tested following a defined order of operations. The tests in liquid phase were performed using 0.1 M KHCO_3 aqueous electrolyte in the cathode and 0.1 M up to 3.6 M KHCO_3 aqueous electrolyte in the anode. Prior to each test, the catholyte was saturated with a vigorous flow of CO_2 until saturation (pH 6.8). No CO_2 flow was fluxed into the anode.

After measuring the open circuit voltage (OCP), a preliminary cyclic voltammetry (CV) analysis was performed to stabilize the electrocatalyst, from + 0.2 V (vs. RHE) to the set potential then used for the chronoamperometry (CA) test (scan voltage rate = 20 mV s^{-1}). Many CV cycles were necessary to reach a stable behaviour. An example of CV profiles was reported in Fig. S11 in SI.

Once the system reached the steady-state after about 20–30 cycles, the CV analysis was stopped and, after some minutes needed to stabilize and to measure again the OCP, the double-layer technique was used to evaluate the capacitance. This method consists of a further set of CV cycles performed at increasing voltage rate (from 2 up to 50 mV s^{-1}) but in a narrow range of voltage centred around the OCP (± 0.016 V).

Fig. 4a shows an example of CV cycles for the capacitance calculation. The values of current density obtained for each voltage (two points, one for positive and one for negative voltage scan rates) were then plotted (Y-axis) against the voltage scan rate (X-axis), as reported in Fig. 4b. The two straight-line slopes (in absolute value) obtained from the linear regression profiles were averaged and used as the capacitance (in $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$).

After these preliminary CV tests (CVs for electrocatalyst stabilization and for capacitance calculation), a 1.5 h CA test in liquid phase was made. The potentials investigated in liquid phase were - 0.4, - 0.5, - 0.6 and - 0.8 V. All potentials reported in the paper refer to RHE (see calculation in the experimental part). Typically, the same catalyst was tested starting from the lowest voltage (-0.4 V) and finishing to the highest voltage (-0.8 V). However, the electrolyte was changed and the system washed after each set voltage. The whole protocol (pre-CVs, CA and post-CVs) was performed for each set voltage. During the CA tests, both gas and liquid products were analysed. The gases products were analysed by Gas chromatography, as reported in the experimental part, sampling the outlet gas stream at constant time interval (10 min), while the liquid products were collected in the catholyte and analysed by GC- IC and GC-MS at the end of the CA. The same CV analysis cycles were then repeated after the CA test.

Fig. 4. a) CV cycles and b) current density vs. scan voltage rate plots for the calculations of capacitance (double layer technique), for a $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{GDL}$ electrode with 10 mg cm^{-2} loading, before a CA at - 0.8 V vs. RHE.

Fig. 5. **a)** Chronoamperometry (CA) and **b)** cyclic voltammetry (CV) profiles for $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{GDL}$ catalyst (10 mg cm^{-2}) for an electrochemical test at -0.4 V vs RHE.

Fig. 5 shows the CA and CV profiles obtained with a test at -0.4 V vs RHE for a Cu_2O GDL with 10 mg cm^{-2} loading. At this applied potential (-0.4 V), after 10–15 min the current density gradually increased (in negative) during the CA (see Fig. 5a), reaching a final value of about -1.25 mA cm^{-2} . We excluded that the increase of the current density was due to the loss of hydrophobicity of the GDL substrate (as shown by the stable current density obtained by testing the bare GDL, see Fig. S12 in SI), but this instead indicates an activation of the electrocatalyst during the test. This hypothesis was confirmed by the CV steady-state profile performed after the CA, evidencing a higher current density and a reduction onset at lower potential with respect the preliminary CV before the CA (compare CV profiles in Fig. 5b). The reported CV profiles in Fig. 5b refer to the steady-state conditions (the latest CV cycle after stabilization). The reasons are likely to ascribed to a partial reduction of copper oxide nanoparticles (on their external surface part) to metallic Cu (due to the highly reductive environment at the cathode) forming a core shell-type system that enhances the current density during the test. It was reported that the co-presence of metallic Cu and Cu oxide can be beneficial for CO_2 reduction [67–70]. The same behaviour was observed for $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{GDL}$ with 5 mg cm^{-2} loading, but not for $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{GDL}$ with 1 mg cm^{-2} and for CuO/GDL with 5 mg cm^{-2} (see CV profiles in Fig. S13 in SI). XRD analysis for the latter electrodes, in fact, did not show the presence of metallic copper.

Electrocatalytic tests in liquid phase

The effect of Cu_2O loading onto GDL substrate was investigated from 1 to 10 mg cm^{-2} . Fig. 6 shows current density and C1 production rate (HCOOH and CO) vs. the applied voltage during the chro-

noamperometry test (CA). The electrochemical behaviour of the bare GDL (no Cu_2O deposited) is also reported. All the values reported in Fig. 6 (and in all next figures) refer to at least two electrochemical tests and close within 5% of error determination (see the error bars on the graphs). Oxalic acid was also produced in small amount, especially at lower potential. Oxalic acid (which is a C2 product) is a very interesting compound used in various industries (mainly pharmaceutical), but it is not usually observed as CO_2 reduction product. The formation of oxalic acid needs only two electrons from each molecule of CO_2 (like formic acid and CO) but a C-C bond is to be formed for its production. The reaction mechanism refers to the reaction between two CO_2^{*-} anion radicals. However, this coupling reaction depends on how long the CO_2^{*-} species are present on the electrode surface and it is usually unfavoured by the presence of water [71]. This can explain why we observed the formation of oxalic acid only at lower potential, but further experimentation is needed to clarify its formation in our conditions.

Fig. 6. C1 production rate (HCOOH and CO) and current density for Cu₂O/GDL electrodes at different catalyst loadings tested in liquid phase.

The current density increased from 1 to 5 mg cm⁻² for each applied voltage, with an increment of current much higher by increasing the voltage. However, only a slight variation was obtained increasing further the Cu₂O loading from 5 to 10 mg cm⁻². The maximum current density was 33.0 mA cm⁻² for 10 mg cm⁻² Cu₂O/GDL at -0.8 V (vs. RHE).

The pH at the cathode (0.1 KHCO₃ aqueous solution saturated with CO₂) was initially 6.8, and it only slightly increased at the end of the CA due to proton consumption for reduction (to a maximum of pH=7.0 in 1.5 h of testing).

After the CA, the liquid electrolyte at the cathode was analysed, as well as the gaseous flow coming out from the liquid reservoir (as reported in the experimental part), to quantify the CO₂ reduction products. The only liquid product detected in these liquid-phase tests was formic acid (except for small amounts of oxalic acid at lower potential, as explained above), while CO and H₂ were found in the gaseous exit stream. No methane, ethylene or alcohols were detected from liquid-phase tests, at least within the detection limits of our analytical instrumentation (see experimental part). For the electrode with 1 mg·cm⁻² loading, the productivity increases with the applied voltage, with a maximum of 8.7 μmol·h⁻¹ at -0.8 V. For higher catalyst loadings (5 and 10 mg·cm⁻²), instead, the C1 production rates reached a maximum at -0.6 V (8.7 and 12.8 μmol·h⁻¹, respectively), then decreasing at -0.8 V. Note that in the adopted electrochemical protocol each electrode was tested in series starting from -0.4 V until -0.8 V, but replacing the electrolyte solutions after each cycle/voltage. We tried to perform an experiment in liquid phase also at -1.0 V (vs. RHE), but we observed a very high current density (about 106 mA cm⁻²) that caused a high instability in the system due to the formation of many gas bubbles (mainly H₂). Thus, at -1.0 V we were able to make EIS measurements but not to quantify CO₂ reduction products as the test was stopped after a short time.

Fig. 7a shows the behaviour of capacitance (in μF cm⁻²) for the Cu₂O/GDL electrodes at different loadings. In particular, the plot reports the capacitance values calculated before the first CA at lower voltage (-0.4 V) in comparison with the final value of capacitance after the latest CA at higher voltage (-0.8 V). The capacitance of each Cu₂O/GDL electrode increased after the whole series of tests with respect to its initial value. Moreover, while in general the initial capacitance values were independently of the catalyst loading, a strong variation of the final capacitance values was observed increasing the catalyst loading. The maximum capacitance value (14.3 μF·cm⁻²) was obtained for 10 mg·cm⁻² loading at the end of CA at -0.8 V.

Fig. 7b shows the product distribution between these two products in terms of CO selectivity (%) at different applied voltage (from -0.4 to -0.8 V). We observed that copper loading had a strong influence on the formation of CO, especially from 1 to 5 mg cm⁻². In detail, no carbon monoxide was produced at the lowest applied voltage (-0.4 V). The formation of CO was observed from -0.5 V, then increasing at -0.6 V with a maximum of 67% for 10 mg cm⁻² loading Cu₂O/GDL electrode. At higher voltage (-0.8 V), the CO

selectivity was lower for all the electrodes (in the range 25–45%) and formic acid formation was favoured.

As described in the experimental part, the calcination of Cu_2O powder leads to the full oxidation of copper. The resulting CuO (Cu II) was deposited onto the GDL (with a final catalyst loading of 5 mg cm^{-2}) and tested in liquid-phase CO_2 reduction. The capacitance values (in $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$) for the CuO/GDL electrodes tested in liquid phase at different potentials are reported in Table S1 in SI, in comparison with gas-phase results.

CuO/GDL was then tested in liquid-phase CO_2 electro-reduction, achieving better performance with respect to Cu_2O electrodes (see SI). Thus, we used CuO/GDL electrodes for comparing the electrocatalytic behaviour in liquid- and gas-phase operations.

The performances of CuO electrode at different applied potentials are reported in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7. (a) Capacitance values for $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{GDL}$ electrodes at different catalyst loadings. Comparison between the values before the first CA at lower voltage (-0.4 V) and the final values after the latest CA at higher voltage (-0.8 V). (b) Selectivity to carbon monoxide vs. applied voltage for $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{GDL}$ electrodes at different catalyst loadings.

Fig. 8. a) Production rate ($\mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$) and b) carbon Faradaic selectivity vs. applied voltage for CuO/GDL electrode ($5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) tested in liquid phase. The current density profile is also reported in both the graphs.

Specifically, Fig. 8a shows the production rate ($\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) and current density ($\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) vs. the applied voltage during the chronoamperometry tests (CA). The current density increased with the applied voltage, reaching a maximum value of $31.4 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at -0.8 V . The main carbon products observed in liquid phase were CO, formic acid and oxalic acid (they are all reduction products requiring two electrons). The production rate of formic acid increased with the applied potential until $7.2 \mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$ at -0.8 V . Increasing further the applied potential (at -1.0 V) was critical due to the very large formation of gases (mainly CO and H_2) creating many bubbles negatively impacting on the electrical contacts with a consequent rapid decrease of the current density, as also occurred for $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}/\text{GDL}$ electrode. Fig. 8b shows, instead, the carbon Faradaic selectivity (FS, %) vs. the applied voltage during the chronoamperometry test (CA), while the chemical selectivity (moles produced/total CO_2 moles converted) for the same electrocatalytic tests is shown in Fig. S15 in SI. The FS (%) to formic acid decreased slightly from -0.4 to -0.6 V (28.8% and 24.3%, respectively), then increasing until 63.5% at -0.8 V at the expense of CO.

Oxalic acid was observed only at lower potential, being the main carbon product at -0.4 V .

Electrocatalytic tests in gas phase

The same CuO/GDL electrode ($5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) reported above for liquid-phase tests was also studied in gas-phase operations. The electrode was tested in series at two different potentials (-0.4 and -1.0 V vs. RHE). For the test at -0.4 V , an aqueous 0.1 M KHCO_3 solution (pH 8.3) was used as the anodic electrolyte (no electrolyte in the cathodic part of the cell where CO_2 reduction occurs). A salt-saturated solution (3.6 M KHCO_3 , pH 8.7) is required (at the anode side) in the test at -1.0 V to prevent the rapid depletion of OH^- , due to the counter oxidation reaction (i.e., water oxidation to oxygen). No CO_2 was fluxed into the anolyte solution.

The electrocatalytic tests in gas phase were performed by following the same protocol described in 3.3

section (including CV analysis and capacitance measurements before and after the CA). The capacitance values (in $\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$) for the CuO/GDL electrodes tested in gas phase at different potentials are reported in Table S1 in SI.

Fig. S16 (in SI) shows the steady-state CV profiles obtained before and after the CA at - 0.4 and - 1.0 V. While a current decrease can be observed for the test at - 0.4 V after the CA (see Fig. S16a), the CV test at - 1.0 V showed a current increase (from 5.5 to 10.2 mA cm^{-2} , see Fig. S16b), which can be ascribed to an in-situ activation of the electrocatalyst at this applied potential. Moreover, the onset of proton reduction was more negative (-0.5 V vs. 0 V vs. RHE, respectively) at higher potential. This behaviour was confirmed by observing the current profiles during the CA, showing for - 1.0 V an increase of current during time until reaching a value of - 8 mA cm^{-2} in 1 h of reaction (see Fig. S17 in SI).

Fig. 9a shows the production rate ($\mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$) and current density (mA cm^{-2}) vs. the applied voltage during the chronoamperometry test (CA).

At - 0.4 V vs RHE, the formation of low amounts of oxalic acid and isopropanol was observed (with a production rate of 0.55 and 0.02 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively) at a current density of 2.3 $\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, while traces of CO are detected only at the end of reactions. At high applied potential (-1.0 V vs RHE), instead, CO, acetaldehyde and ethanol were detected with a production rate of 10.6, 0.21 and 0.9 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively. Traces of acetic acid (C2), propionaldehyde (C3) and butanone (C4) were also found in the liquid absorber. The current density in this case was 7.0 $\text{mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. At the end of the electrocatalytic tests, the used catalysts were soaked for 1 h with a dilute solution of H_2SO_4 (2 mL, 0.001 M) at mild temperature (a few degrees above room temperature) to favour the desorption of organic compounds remained absorbed on the catalyst surface. Traces of ethanol were detected only for the test at - 1.0 V, confirming the production of this C2 product for this applied potential.

Fig. S19 in SI shows two SEM images of the used CuO/GDL electrode.

Fig. 9. (a) Production rate ($\mu\text{mol h}^{-1}$) and (b) carbon Faradaic selectivity vs. applied voltage for CuO/GDL electrode (5 mg cm^{-2}) tested in gas phase. The current density profile is also reported in both the graphs.

Fig. 9b reports the carbon Faradaic selectivity (FS, %) vs. the applied voltage during the chronoamperometry test (CA), while the chemical selectivity (moles produced/total CO₂ moles converted) for the same electrocatalytic tests is shown in Fig. S18 in SI. Note that at - 1.0 V the FS (%) to ethanol is much higher than its chemical selectivity (34.2 vs 14.0%, respectively), as CO₂ reduction to ethanol requires 12 electrons.

A strong modification in the morphology of CuO was observed after the gas-phase electrocatalytic tests, as the nanocube structure was partially replaced by the formation of nanorods with diameter of about 200 nm and length around 5–15 μm. This modification can explain the enhanced current density obtained from CV analysis at the end of the last test at - 1.0 V, and also the different product distribution in gas phase with respect to liquid phase.

A useful comparison between liquid- and gas-phase tests is provided in Fig. 10, showing the specific current density, which is the amount of current (per square meter unit) used to produce the single reduction product. Fig. S21 in SI also shows the cyclic voltammetry of CuO/GDL electrode obtained by flowing CO₂ or inert gas (N₂) in liquid- and gas-phase operations.

Discussion and conclusions

The results presented here evidence a marked impact of the use of liquid- or gas-phase operations on the behaviour of the same copper- based electrocatalyst in CO₂ reduction. The comparison between Figs. 8 and 9 and the direct comparison provided in Fig. 10 clearly remark that both electrocatalytic activity and product distribution are strongly affected by the type of operation. While C₂ products were essentially absent in liquid-phase tests, except minor amounts of oxalic acid at the lower voltages, various C₂ products, particularly ethanol at the higher voltage, but also acetaldehyde, acetic acid and even C₃ products such as isopropanol, were formed. In contrast, formic acid (which was the major product at the higher voltages in liquid-phase operations) was not detected in gas-phase operations. Therefore, a drastic change in product distribution was observed.

Note that, as also commented in the introduction, we used an undoped CuO/GDL electrode (i) because it was prepared by an easy scalable methodology to obtain uniform GDL-based electrodes and (ii) to avoid introducing other elements that could alter EIS results. The goal, in fact, was not to optimize the catalyst for achieving maximum CO₂ reduction performance, but to prepare an electrode able to give reliable indications on the differences between liquid- and gas-phase operations. There is a well correspondence between EIS (and CV) and catalytic experiments in showing the differences between these two types of operations, as shown by EIS experiments with CO₂ and N₂ feeds (Fig. 3) and by charge transfer resistance calculations (Table 1). In liquid-phase operations, EIS results demonstrate that (i) proton reduction is dominant and (ii) protons compete with intermediate CO₂ species in the adsorption onto the electrocatalytic active sites, favouring their early desorption to produce CO and formic acid (both needing only two electrons). In gas-phase operations, instead, EIS data show that (i) the local concentration of CO₂ on the electrode surface is higher with respect to the actual amount of CO₂ in liquid-phase operations (limited by its low solubility) and (ii) proton supplying becomes the limiting step. Thus, the properties of these electrodes, and in turn the selectivity paths of CO₂ electro-reduction are largely determined by transport limitations rather than only by the intrinsic properties of the electrocatalysts, which instead most of literature studies and review papers have focused on. EIS results also demonstrate that, in the absence of the redox element Cu_xO (i.e., only the bare GDL), there was a very low charge transfer.

Fig. 10. Specific current density vs. applied voltage for CuO/GDL electrode ($5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) tested in **a)** liquid phase and **b)** gas phase.

EIS data (Fig. 3) show a change in charge transfer resistance at a potential of -0.6 V (vs. RHE). Interestingly, electrocatalytic data (Fig. 6) in liquid phase present a change in behaviour at the same applied potential (-0.6 V), with a decrease in C1 production rate (for the higher loadings) and a sharp increase in current density passing from -0.6 to -0.8 V , as well as a decrease in CO selectivity (Fig. 7b) and increase in formic acid productivity and Faradaic selectivity (FS) (Fig. 8). The variation of the EIS response with the applied potential in liquid phase indicates a change in the transport (ionic migration) towards the reaction site above this threshold voltage. Thus, the rate of H^+ transport to the electrocatalyst increases, with an increase in H_2 formation (enhanced current density) and availability of H_2 to react with CO to form formic acid. On the other hand, the increase of the potential determines an accelerated transport of the CO_2 anion radical (i.e., the species formed by one electron transfer to CO_2), thus decreasing its concentration and availability for further electron transfer but also its electrocatalytic oxidative dimerization to form oxalic acid. In fact, the latter product was determined only at lower applied voltage.

EIS data are in well agreement with the electrocatalytic results in CO_2 reduction, and evidence how productivity and selectivity are driven by diffusion problems (of protons and CO_2 intermediate species) depending on the applied voltage. By increasing the potential, the rate of electron transfer increases and then productivity, but the surface coverage results affected by the different accessibility (diffusion) of CO_2 and protons to the electrocatalyst surface and in turn the selectivity results rather influenced. Thus, EIS experiments prove the important concept of how the selectivity path is determined by the complex aspects governing the diffusion of reactants to the electrocatalyst surface by changing the applied potential.

In gas-phase experiments, by avoiding the bulk electrolyte, CO_2 diffusion is no longer affected by its concentration in the electrolyte, while diffusion of protons to the electrocatalyst surface is more difficult (becoming the rate limiting step) due to the need to diffuse first through the Nafion membrane (in direct contact with the GDE) and then by surface diffusion through the electrocatalyst. This, in turn, determines a change in the paths of surface reactions, favouring the formation of C2 products (Fig. 10), but a lower productivity and current density (compare Figs. 8 and 9), due to the lower availability of protons. It is also evident from these elements that the optimization of the behaviour in liquid- and gas-phase operations require different strategies, in the latter by accelerating the transport and mobility of protons to the electrocatalyst, for example by working at higher temperature, or by designing the GDL to facilitate the surface transport of protons, or by using water-saturated CO_2 as feed.

In conventional electrocatalytic cells (liquid phase) the GDE and membrane are not in contact, and the liquid electrolyte (i.e., the catholyte) is interposed between them. The distance between the GDE and the membrane causes an additional resistance increasing the cell voltage needed to reach the desired voltage at the working electrode. In gas-phase systems, instead, as no liquid electrolyte is used at the cathode, the GDE

and membrane are in direct contact each other (zero-gap configuration) forming a Membrane Electrode Assembly (MEA) in analogy with fuel cell technology. This influences not only the resistance but also the mass transport and the reactivity in the vicinity of the active sites.

Moreover, we observed that in our conditions the CuO/GDL behaves slightly better than Cu₂O/GDL (Fig. S14), differently from other literature results that observed superior performances for Cu₂O [72–75]. In our case, in fact, Cu₂O is not stable and undergoes some modifications during the electrochemical operation. EIS (coupled with other electrochemical methods like CV, chronoamperometry, see Figs. S16 and S17) is a useful strategy to monitor the modifications of the electrocatalyst/electrode, in addition to the conventional characterization methods. The differences in behaviour could be ascribed to these changes, but it should be noted that for the preparation of the electrocatalyst we used a simple procedure, suitable for scale-up to larger size and for industrial exploitability.

In addition, we have adopted a cell design and operation conditions relevant for industrial use. Under these experimental conditions, the behaviour, as commented above, is determined from mass transfer effects rather than the catalyst itself, and for this reason its characteristics may affect less the overall behaviour. On the other hand, these results may in turn put the question of whether some of literature results could also be determined by variations in the diffusion transport to the electrocatalyst, induced by changes in the electrode itself, rather than by intrinsic properties of the electrocatalyst.

We could also note that cyclic voltammetry (CV) results (Fig. S16) show that the modification occurring in situ to the electrocatalyst depends on the applied potential. In gas-phase tests, a peculiar transformation of the nanostructure, from packed nanocubes (Fig. S10) to nanorod shape with diameter of about 200 nm and length from around 5–15 μm (Fig. S19), was observed. This change can explain the enhanced current density obtained from CV analysis at the end of the last test at -1.0 V. This reconstruction did not occur in liquid-phase operations, evidencing again that liquid- and gas-phase operations behave in significantly different ways. Many aspects (including diffusion of protons and CO₂-adspecies to the electrocatalyst surface) should be considered to evaluate the electrocatalytic performance.

Electrochemical characterization methods like EIS, CV and CA are thus a complementary and necessary methodology to study electrocatalytic reactions.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.apcatb.2022.121845.

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